

Cover

INSPIRE ***Procurement of Innovation – How INSPIRE*** ***Academy addressed the confidence of*** ***public procurers***

<p><i>When citing, sharing, or adapting this work, please provide proper attribution as follows:</i></p>	<p>Rossana Alessandrello, Suzan Ikävalko.</p> <p>AQuAS - Agency for Health Quality and Assessment of Catalonia, Nordic Healthcare Group (NHG) (Spain, Finland).</p>
<p><i>Abstract</i></p>	<p>INSPIRE received funding from the EU FP7 programme, and was implemented over two years, ending in October 2015. Its main objective was to ‘inspire’ public procurers in both the healthcare and social services sectors towards the adoption of the procurement of innovation. During the project, different initiatives were carried out by the partners; coordinating entity NHG, AQuAS, BITECIC, The European House Ambrosetti, Resah IDF and BBG. Outcomes included the generation of hands-on material for practitioners (toolkits and manuals), the generation of materials for policy makers (analysis of innovation procurement practices and recommendations for its wider adoption) and the active engagement of public procurers and investor communities through the organisation of workshops across Europe (Helsinki, Vienna, Milan, Barcelona, London and Paris). At the end of the project the INSPIRE Academy was able to share its knowledge and materials with European public contracting authorities, venture capitalists, industry players, academia and research organisations.</p> <p>Needs Assessment, Open Technical Dialogue and Business Case Modelling were identified as the basic pillars for the successful public procurement of innovations from the practitioners’ perspective. From the policy makers perspective: national action plans orientating funding incentives to public procurers and providing coordination support to public procurers engaging in public procurement of innovations were identified as successful practices to incentivise their wider deployment.</p> <p>As a project result INSPIRE consortium members also initiated several concrete innovative procurement actions such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">* Smart Ambulance SAEPP: http://www.smartambulanceproject.eu/* EIPonAHA Procurement Platform: https://ec.europa.eu/eip/ageing/public-procurement-platform_en* PRO4VIP: http://www.pro4vip.eu/* ANTISUPERBUGS PCP: http://antisuperbugs.eu/* RITMOCORE PPI: http://www.ritmocore-ppi.eu/

INSPIRE

Procurement of Innovation – How INSPIRE Academy addressed the confidence of public procurers

Rossana Alessandrello, Suzan Ikävalko,
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(Spain, Finland)

INSPIRE received funding from the EU FP7 programme, and was implemented over two years, ending in October 2015. Its main objective was to 'inspire' public procurers in both the healthcare and social services sectors towards the adoption of the procurement of innovation. During the project, different initiatives were carried out by the partners; coordinating entity NHG, AQuAS, BITECIC, The European House Ambrosetti, Resah IDF and BBG. Outcomes included the generation of hands-on material for practitioners (toolkits and manuals), the generation of materials for policy makers (analysis of innovation procurement practices and recommendations for its wider adoption) and the active engagement of public procurers and investor communities through the organisation of workshops across Europe (Helsinki, Vienna, Milan, Barcelona, London and Paris). At the end of the project the INSPIRE Academy was able to share its knowledge and materials with European public contracting authorities, venture capitalists, industry players, academia and research organisations.

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AT A GLANCE

Programme:	Seventh Framework Programme - FP7
Duration:	01.10.2013 - 30.09.2015
Main outcome:	Strengthening innovative procurement strategies in eHealth, active aging and independent living
Website:	www.inspirecampus.eu

procurers and providing coordination support to public procurers engaging in public procurement of innovations were identified as successful practices to incentivise their wider deployment.

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- * Smart Ambulance SAEPP:
<http://www.smartambulanceproject.eu/>
- * EIPonAHA Procurement Platform:
https://ec.europa.eu/eip/ageing/public-procurement-platform_en
- * PRO4VIP
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- * ANTISUPERBUGS PCP
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- * RITMOCORE PPI
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RELIEF PCP

How to innovate in the chronic pain field

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RELIEF is a H2020 project (GA n° 689476) coordinated by BravoSolution Spain, which is a leading group focused on strategic procurement processes.

The main objective of the project is to prepare and execute a Pre-Commercial Procurement tender to find innovative ICT solutions that improve the self-management of chronic pain patients.

The project has received funding of almost 2 million euros and is composed of 6 partners from Spain, France and Sweden, of which three are public health procurers (Servicio Andaluz de Salud – SAS in Spain, Réseau des Acheteurs Hospitaliers – RESAH IDF in France and Uppsala County Council – CCU in Sweden); additional supporting partners are the Hospital Federation of France – SPH Conseil and one Research Group from the Open University of Catalonia – UOC.

During the first year of the project, the RELIEF consortium has worked on validation at the buyer group level of the common unmet needs to accurately define RELIEF's common challenge: How to improve the self-management of chronic pain patients?

AT A GLANCE

Programme:	Horizont 2020
Duration:	01.12.2015 – 30.11.2019
Main outcome:	The design, research and development of a data-driven, Internet-of-Everything (IoE) platform for European cities to enable large-scale co-creation, testing and validation of smart city apps and services
Website:	www.select4cities.eu

